

Variations in winter temperatures over decades: the underside of a French XF story

Soubeyrand S

INRAE, BioSP, 84914 Avignon Cedex 9, France

Xylella fastidiosa was in situ detected in France in 2015 (in Corsica and Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur) but several studies, grounded on phylogenetic and population-dynamics models, trace the emergence of *Xylella* in Corsica from the 50's to the 80's (at least with regard to the strains observed since 2015). At this temporal scale (i.e., at the scale of the decades separating the emergence of *Xylella* and its detection), *Xylella* and its vector(s) encountered definitively diverse climatic conditions, because of both weather variations and climate change. They especially encountered varying winter temperatures, which are classically used to build proxies of *Xylella* presence or severity. Combining knowledge from the literature, surveillance data and a parsimonious dynamic model that explicitly takes into account the spatio-temporal variation in winter temperatures, I will (i) present possible past propagation scenarios up to the detection of *Xylella*, (ii) disentangle the impact of annual variation in winter temperatures in these scenarios, (iii) assess the impact of surveillance and control measures in the contemporary period, and (iii) draw forecasts of the sanitary situation during the next decades grounded on different representative pathways of CO₂ concentration. Such an analysis, based on a dynamic vision of the spatial distribution of *Xylella* over broad temporal horizons, could become an interesting tool to informing the choices and the timing of strategies for eradication, containment, living with, etc.

Keywords: population dynamics, epidemic scenarios, spatio-temporel modeling